

6G ✦ REFERENCE

D5.1

Dissemination, Exploitation &
Communication Plans

AUSTRALO

WP5

Ecosystem Building, Outreach &
Exploitation

Revision v1

Work package	WP5
Task	T5.1, T5.2 T5.3 T5.4
Due date	30-06-2024
Submission date	28-06-2024
Deliverable lead	AUSTRALO
Version	V1
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Abstract

This document offers a thorough overview of the project's dissemination, exploitation, standardisation and communication strategies, highlighting the target groups and their segments in detail. It also describes the project's online presence, including the project website and social media platforms. Furthermore, the document outlines the exploitation strategies of the project to enhance the impact and reach, as well as the standardisation activities plan.

Keywords

Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, Sustainability, Standardisation, Ecosystem Building, SNS Collaboration, Stakeholders, Agile, Outreach

Document revision history

Version	Date	Description of change	Authors
V0.1	10-05-2024	Table of contents, Communication, Dissemination part	Antonis Sapountzis (AUS)
V0.2	30-05-2024	Standardisation, Exploitation part	Stefan Andersson (EAB)
V0.3	21-06-2024	Figures, Corrections	Antonis Sapountzis (AUS)
V0.4	25-06-2024	2-staged Review	I. Llamas-Garro (CTTC) E.A.M. Klumperink (UT)
V1	28-06-2024	Final Version	Antonis Sapountzis (AUS)

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Document information

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CL	Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
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* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

Executive Summary

The 6G-REFERENCE Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Plans document contains the project's comprehensive strategies for dissemination, communication, exploitation, and standardisation activities. This document is the result of a collaborative effort among the project partners, taking into account stakeholder requirements and the partners' communication channels and tools. Serving as a supportive resource, the plans aim to enhance the effectiveness of each partner's dissemination efforts, ensuring collective high visibility for the project's activities and outcomes. It presents a selection of communication and dissemination tools and activities tailored to engage the project's target groups. Additionally, the plan includes an outline of exploitation strategies designed to maximise the project's impact and reach, leveraging the project's outcomes and results to their full potential. The standardisation activity plans will focus on establishing connections and synergies with relevant standardisation bodies aiming to facilitate and advocate for the inclusion of its outcomes in future new or revised industry standards.

To amplify the impact of dissemination activities, a multi-faceted and multi-channel approach is proposed, with materials and tools customised to align with the target audience's specific needs, interests, and engagement potential. The 6G-REFERENCE consortium views this plan as a dynamic document, reflecting an inclusive and continuous dialogue with potential users and affiliated networks throughout the project to ensure optimal outcomes.

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Acronyms and definitions

ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuit
C&D	Communication & Dissemination
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
IP	Intellectual Property
IA	Industry Association
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
JU	Joint Undertaking
OTT	Over The Top
Qx	Quarter x
R&D	Research and Development
RTD	Research and Technical Development
SNS	Smart Networks and Services
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

Research and innovation are vital drivers of economic growth, job creation, and societal well-being. Effectively communicating and disseminating the knowledge generated through research and innovation initiatives is crucial to ensure this knowledge reaches and benefits society. The primary means of achieving this is through the commercialisation of products and services, which serves as a key pathway for sharing research outcomes with the public.

Furthermore, sharing research findings can accelerate Research and Technical Development (RTD) efforts, improving the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) and paving the way for new research frontiers in emerging and evolving trends. Additionally, dissemination activities, such as participating in workshops/conferences or publishing information on websites, empower stakeholders to expand their knowledge, stay informed on the latest advancements, receive feedback on economic viability, and identify market-driven avenues for exploitation.

This document presents the 6G-REFERENCE's Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Plans, which outlines the project's comprehensive strategies for dissemination, communication, exploitation and standardisation (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Dissemination, Communication, Standardisation and Exploitation Plans

The plans presented in this document have been developed through a collaborative effort among the project partners, taking into account the categories and requirements of stakeholders, as well as the communication channels and tools available to the partners. This document serves as a supportive resource for each partner to enhance the impact of their dissemination efforts, ensuring the project's activities and results receive significant visibility. The plans propose a diverse range of communication and

dissemination tools and activities to engage the target audiences in the 6G-REFERENCE project effectively.

To reach this goal, a diverse strategy is suggested to maximise the effect of these activities, which includes customising materials and resources to cater to the specific needs, interests, and involvement levels of the intended audiences. The consortium sees this plan as an evolving document that will be revised based on ongoing discussions with the project members, stakeholders and relevant networks to achieve the best results.

1.1. Document Structure

This deliverable is organised as follows to align with these high-level objectives:

- **Executive Summary:** Includes a summary of the document content.
- **Section 1:** Introduction provides the deliverable's general context, scope and structure.
- **Section 2:** Stakeholder Management provides a clear overview of 6G-REFERENCE's Stakeholder Engagement Plans, which outline the methodology for identifying and engaging with high-interest stakeholders, groups, initiatives, or individuals.
- **Section 3:** Dissemination & Communication strategy offers a comprehensive overview of the outreach strategy timeline and performance metrics.
- **Section 4:** Exploitation and Sustainability Plans outlines key exploitation principles related to the project while introducing a clear plan for defining the right exploitation channel for the project's assets.
- **Section 5:** Standardisation Plans initiates the discussion around the standardisation plan of the project and its contributions to standardisation activities.
- **Section 6:** Conclusions summarise the key points of this deliverable.
- **Section 7:** The appendix lists the KPIs and C&D tools.

1.2. Related Task and Deliverables

This document outlines a comprehensive strategy for disseminating, communicating, and exploiting 6G-REFERENCE's outcomes, and it is released as part of the tasks in WP5:

- **Task 5.1** Dissemination and Communication Plans
- **Task 5.2** Innovation Management, Exploitation and Sustainability
- **Task 5.3** Standardisation Activities
- **Task 5.4** Ecosystem Building and SNS Collaboration

Aligned with these tasks, the report is connected to upcoming deliverables of **WP5**, including:

D5.2 Dissemination, Communication & Engagement Intermediate Report (M18, AUS): This report will encompass the actions and outcomes accomplished regarding awareness and engagement strategies in the project's initial phase.

D5.3 Dissemination, Communication & Engagement Final Report (M36, AUS):

It will document the actions and outcomes accomplished in relation to awareness and engagement strategies during the second phase of the project.

D5.4 Impact Assessment, Exploitation & Standards Intermediate Report (M18, EAB): The report will focus on the anticipated impact and the management of the innovation of the results. It will offer information on the standardisation activities, the exploitation model, analysis of the business plan, exploitation routes, etc.

D5.5 Impact Assessment, Exploitation & Standards Final Report (M36, EAB): The report will include an assessment of the anticipated impact and oversee the innovation of the results. It will incorporate information about standardisation, the exploitation model, analysis of the business plan, exploitation routes, and more.

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2. Stakeholder Management

2.1. Stakeholder Engagement Plans

Identifying and engaging with the most relevant stakeholders is often referred to as 'ecosystem building' and is a fundamental aspect of every Horizon Europe project, such as 6G-REFERENCE. The program heavily relies on communities, initiatives, and projects that will either utilise the outcomes or engage and potentially collaborate with its activities throughout its duration. Establishing and nurturing an ecosystem of key players around an initiative is a critical factor in determining the outcomes and success of its value stream. The stakeholders' influence on a project is contingent upon their potential power - their capacity to impact the value proposition - and their interest in exerting that influence. Evaluating the relative levels of each factor guides the decision-making process on where to invest time and resources to achieve the most significant benefits.

In the realm of addressing fundamental challenges in Research and Innovation, numerous initiatives often operate independently to tackle the same issue from various angles, resulting in inefficiencies and a failure to realise their full potential. By embracing an open collaboration framework with peers and groups that can benefit from and contribute to the project's impact, 6G-REFERENCE will gain a deeper understanding of the requirements and advantages of aligning efforts with similar task forces. This approach necessitates a flexible growth factor capable of exploring and fostering entirely new synergies throughout the project's lifecycle, enabling a competitive edge and expanding its sphere of influence.

2.1.1. Target Groups & Stakeholders

Stakeholders are the core of the dissemination, communication, and exploitation efforts of the 6G-REFERENCE project. The project has identified the key target stakeholder groups, and the main goals are to:

- Increase stakeholder awareness of its activities and outcomes.
- Promote the utilisation of the project's openly accessible results.
- Outline how stakeholders can continue to leverage the project's outcomes in a sustainable manner, even after the project's completion.

To effectively raise awareness of 6G-REFERENCE and drive stakeholder engagement, it is critical to clearly identify the 'target audience' (**Figure 2**). Understanding these stakeholder profiles and their influence within the value chain is essential for crafting impactful Communication, Dissemination, Standardisation and Exploitation strategies.

Figure 2. Target Groups

6G Ecosystems: This stakeholder category surrounds the professional profiles engaged in research, innovation, business activities, and standardisation efforts surrounding 6G virtualised RAN disaggregated architecture. These individuals represent the core audience for the 6G-REFERENCE project. These profiles are dedicated to investigating, advancing, and demonstrating the technical capabilities offered by advanced communication and computing functionalities. This includes high-performance base station management, trusted end-to-end services, and an open multi-vendor architecture.

Microelectronics Ecosystem: This segment comprises experts from across Europe, from antenna ICs to digital processing, RF and mixed-signal designers, communications and signal processing, radar and remote sensing, as well as hardware manufacturers and providers.

Partnerships & Networks: The 6G-REFERENCE project aims to capitalise on the collaborative potential of initiatives advocating for 6G, computing, and microelectronics in Europe. By leveraging the consortium's leadership and participation in various ecosystems, the project will work to create synergies and bridge the collaboration between the '6G Ecosystems' and the 'Microelectronics Ecosystem'. This strategic approach will enable the project to harness the complementary expertise, resources, and networks available within these interconnected domains.

Application Sectors: The project aims to generate interest and engagement from application sector groups, which contain Developers and Over-The-Top (OTT) providers, as well as vertically-oriented sectors with high throughput and latency requirements, such as media, manufacturing, and mobility.

Policymakers: These stakeholders are responsible for setting the rules, guidelines, and public incentives that shape the European strategy and drive the continent's digital transformation, human capital development, and overall competitiveness. By engaging with this stakeholder group, the project aims to gain insights into the evolving policy

frameworks, funding programs, and regulatory environments that will ultimately influence the successful implementation and adoption of 6G technologies.

2.1.2. Stakeholder Map

The diagram presented below (**Figure 3**) illustrates the initial iteration of the 6G-REFERENCE Stakeholders Map, visually depicting the intended recipients of the project's outputs at this phase. This stakeholder map has been developed based on the various stakeholder groups identified thus far and is the result of the ongoing cycle within the Agile Stakeholder Framework. It is important to note that this document is dynamic, undergoing updates every two months to ensure its continued relevance and accuracy as the project progresses.

Figure 3. Stakeholder Map

2.1.3. Engagement Plan

The stakeholders are engaged in the project through agile cycles (see **Figure 4**) corresponding to major ongoing research activities or accomplishments. The objective of these cycles is to leverage the project's impact among the different target groups, creating a sustainable footprint for 6G-REFERENCE.

Figure 4. Stakeholder Engagement (Agile) Cycles

Each agile cycle (Sprint Qx) includes three phases:

- **Scouting** - This phase involves identifying and mapping the relevant and interested parties, whether they are individuals or organisations.
- **Interacting** - In this phase, the 6G-REFERENCE team reaches out to the identified stakeholders through personalised one-on-one communication, such as email or meetings, as well as leveraging the project's established communication channels.
- **Learning** - The insights gained from the exchanges are analysed to inform and optimise the approach for the next stakeholder engagement cycle.

Figure 5, presented below, showcases the initial version of the 6G-REFERENCE Stakeholder Involvement Tuning Map Quadrant. This graphical representation provides an overview of the primary target audiences, taking into account the various stakeholder groups identified thus far through the 1st Cycle of the Agile Stakeholder Framework. The Stakeholders Involvement Tuning Map Quadrant serves as a strategic tool for stakeholder management, enabling the project team to map the levels of interest and influence that different stakeholders hold in relation to the 6G-REFERENCE initiative. This visual aid will help the project navigate the stakeholder landscape and tailor its engagement and communication strategies accordingly.

Figure 5. Stakeholder Involvement Tuning Map Quadrant

Actively Engage Quadrant: It focuses on stakeholders and target groups that have a significant influence on the project while the project demonstrates a strong interest in them.

Keep Satisfied Quadrant: This quadrant comprises organisations and individuals with substantial decision-making authority but limited availability for active project

engagement. Maintaining consistent communication with this group is important, considering their valuable feedback and aligning project activities with their directives.

Keep Informed Quadrant: It includes organisations and individuals (or EU projects) directly linked to our project. While they may have limited impact or influence on 6G-REFERENCE activities, exploring synergies for joint communication and dissemination is essential.

Monitor Quadrant: It targets entities with limited impact on project tasks and little capacity for active involvement. While not central to project activities, regular communication is key to staying informed and alert for quadrant changes.

The project will also involve gathering feedback through consultations during the stakeholder engagement process. This could include brief surveys or interviews to capture external perspectives on the project and its operations. By collecting feedback from stakeholders in this way, the project team can gain valuable insights and external viewpoints. This will help them better understand the needs, concerns, and expectations of the different target groups involved in or impacted by the 6G-REFERENCE project. Incorporating this feedback loop into the agile engagement cycles will allow the project to continuously adapt and refine its approach, ensuring it remains responsive to the evolving needs of the stakeholder community. This collaborative approach helps to build trust, foster buy-in, and maximise the project's impact and reach.

During the first half of the project, efforts will focus on establishing contacts and collaboration with the SNS ecosystem. In the second half, activities will expand the 6G community beyond this framework.

2.2. SNS Ecosystem Collaboration

2.2.1. Objectives

The objective of dissemination, communication and collaboration within 6G-REFERENCE is to enhance the visibility and knowledge transfer of the project and its findings. The aim is to make the research and validation results accessible and utilised by the European 6G, Microelectronics Ecosystems and collaborate with the SNS JU, 6G-IA Work Groups, CSAs of the program, and other technical initiatives, especially those related to 6G Development in Stream B, thereby aiding in the future implementation of 6G technology.

As part of the SNS JU Governance mode, Working Groups (WGs) will be formed to address certain issues and publish consolidated views established within the SNS Community.

There are three basic types of Working groups:

- **SNS Industry Working Groups (6G IA WGs)** – established under a mandate from the 6G IA.¹
- **SNS JU Project Working groups (SNS JU WGs)** – established under the mandate of the inter-project Steering Board (SB).²
- **SNS Strategic Working Groups (SNS GB WGs)** – established under the mandate of the SNS JU Governing Board (GB).

2.2.2. European Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU)

The European Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking³ (SNS JU) aims to lead Europe in 5G and 6G technologies. Established by Council Regulation 2021/2085, it coordinates resources for Smart Networks and Services, aligning with Member States for 6G research and 5G deployment. With a budget of €900 million for 2021-2027, its missions include fostering 6G technology sovereignty and boosting 5G deployment. The SNS JU supports Europe's technological sovereignty, strategic roadmaps, and public-private membership for funding. It plays a crucial role in advancing digital and green transitions in the economy and society.

Working Groups originating from the SNS JU Projects are referred to as the SNS JU WGs and include:

- 6G Architecture WG.
- Reliable Software Network WG.
- Test, Measurement and KPIs Validation WG.

2.2.3. 6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association (SNS 6G-IA)

The 6G-IA⁴ is a key player in European Industry and Research for next-gen networks. It aims to advance Europe's position in 5G and 6G technologies. Representing the private sector in 5G-PPP and SNS JU, it collaborates with the European Commission. The association unites global telecoms, digital actors, and academia. Engaging in various strategic activities like standardisation and R&D projects emphasises international cooperation and vertical industry partnerships.

SNS Industry Working Groups – also known as the 6G IA Working Groups⁵:

- Vision.
- Open SNS.

¹ <https://6g-ia.eu/6g-ia-working-groups/>

² <https://smart-networks.europa.eu/sns-ju-working-groups/>

³ <https://smart-networks.europa.eu/>

⁴ <https://6g-ia.eu/>

⁵ <https://6g-ia.eu/6g-ia-working-groups/>

- Trials.
- Pre-Standardization.
- 5G/6G for Connected and Automated Mobility.
- Spectrum.
- Security.
- WiTaR.

2.2.4. Sibling Projects

Wireless Communication Technologies and Signal Processing Stream B (2023) focuses on revolutionary advancements in 6G and IoT technologies. This Stream targets low to medium TRL in WP2023, with the objective of delivering innovative solutions for real-life networks over a long period of time.

B-01-05: MICROELECTRONICS-BASED SOLUTIONS FOR 6G NETWORKS⁶

- **FirstTo6G:** Fourier-Domain TRx Solutions Enabling Widespread Realisation Of 6G.
- **TeraGreen:** Towards Energy-Efficient Tbps Wireless Links.

2.2.5. Collaboration Strategy

To achieve the objectives, the project plans to share its outcomes with a diverse audience, encompassing both academic and non-academic stakeholders such as industry experts, policymakers, and the general public. The approach involves various strategies, including Open Science practices like publications, presentations, conferences, workshops, and webinars, as well as active participation in Working Groups within organisations like 6G-IA, 3GPP, and O-RAN alliance. Additionally, targeted campaigns will be implemented to maximise outreach through channels such as the project website, social media, newsletters, and collaboration with 6G-IA for promotional activities. The communication efforts aim to influence policy decisions, inspire further research, raise awareness, support the SNS Joint Undertaking, and foster innovation in the industry. By disseminating the project's results widely, the goal is to advance knowledge and drive positive societal outcomes in the realm of 6G technology.

3. Communication & Dissemination Plans

3.1. Communication Strategy

Effective communication and dissemination play crucial roles in every Horizon Europe project, including 6G-REFERENCE. By carefully designing a dynamic and engaging strategy, the project can optimise its influence by addressing external variables and possible obstacles. While communication and dissemination are viewed as separate yet interconnected elements in this strategy, communication activities entail targeted steps

⁶ <https://smart-networks.europa.eu/phase-2-stream-b/#B5>

to showcase the project's progress and successes, with the goal of effectively involving a broad audience. Strategic campaigns will be crafted and implemented continuously during the project's duration to spark interest among specific audiences, leveraging the consortium's linguistic diversity for a global reach and utilising aspects of the Promotion Mix to amplify outreach and influence.

3.1.1. Objectives

Communication in Research and Innovation initiatives is a thoughtfully strategic procedure that begins at project initiation and continues throughout its entirety, focusing on publicising the project and its results. This process requires strategic and customised methods to interact with diverse groups, such as the media and the general public, enabling potential bidirectional communication. Within the realm of the 6G-REFERENCE project, communication efforts involve tailored actions to exhibit the project and its accomplishments. The communication plan is crafted to engage a wider audience, reaching beyond the project's core community (**Figure 6**).

HOW TO COMMUNICATE YOUR PROJECT

Figure 6. Communication Principles

This strategy aims to connect with a wide audience. Continuous communication efforts will be implemented during the project to attract the attention of the intended audience, emphasising the technological progress and pilot projects of 6G-REFERENCE. These strategies will utilise the Promotion Mix, a part of the Marketing Mix (**Figure 7**), to enhance awareness and promote audience participation. In the framework of 6G-REFERENCE, this Promotion Mix includes incorporating Personal Selling, Digital Marketing, Promotional Materials, and Branding.

Figure 7. The Marketing Mix

The communication plan aims to:

- Set up internal communication channels within the consortium.
- Aid in the external promotion and branding management of 6G-REFERENCE.
- Deliver key project messages to all stakeholders.
- Increase awareness among general audiences regarding the advancements of 6G-REFERENCE.
- Boost awareness and interest in the project.

3.1.2. Phases

The communication plan will unfold in three distinct stages:

- **Phase 1 – Planning and Initial Communication (M1-M6)**

Initiating in M1 of the project, the initial communication phase will primarily focus on planning all operations, establishing essential communication tools and platforms (like the website and social media), and pinpointing potential target audiences and stakeholders. The continuous identification of stakeholders will persist throughout the project's duration. This initial phase also incorporates adaptability: the communication strategy will be regularly reassessed and adjusted to address specific needs or situations. Press releases and other preliminary communication activities will be undertaken during this phase. Agile adjustments to the communication strategy will be made throughout the project based on progress and stakeholder input.

- **Phase 2 – Awareness Communication (M7- M36)**

In this stage, early communication activities will concentrate on raising awareness among the general public and specific groups about the project's presence and upcoming activities. Emphasis will be placed on online tools and strategies for their wider reach compared to traditional methods. Participation in webinars and online events, along with publishing project-related articles, will be part of this phase. Throughout the project duration, this phase will primarily focus on conveying the project's core outcomes to a broad range of stakeholders.

- **Phase 3 – Focused Communication (M19-M36)**

The third communication phase requires the project to have reached a stage of relative maturity, unveiling initial tangible results. This phase will involve targeted communication strategies, such as releasing articles, blogs, or posts highlighting specific project outcomes and advantages, engaging in pertinent external stakeholder events, and crafting tailored communication materials (like videos) for the community. Concurrent with phase 2, this stage is dedicated to focused communication campaigns directed at specific audiences rather than the entire community.

3.1.3. Measures

Various measures (**Table 1**) and communication tools - digital channels (**Table 2**) and promotion materials (**Table 3**) - will be used to ensure the project effectively reaches the appropriate audiences in a communication-friendly and synchronised manner.

Direct Engagement			
Measure	Description	Benefit of measure	Stakeholders
Email Campaigns	Implementing targeted email campaigns aimed at stakeholders to enhance awareness regarding the projects and their undertakings.	Email communication with a specific set of contacts is a highly efficient approach to engagement, especially when disseminating information about activities and outcomes across diverse ecosystems.	6G & Microelectronics Ecosystems, Partnerships & Networks
One-to-one Meetings	Maintaining ongoing interactions with selected stakeholders, involving them in forthcoming initiatives, and sustaining a consistent communication channel.	Although not scalable, one-on-one meetings prove effective when concentrating on specific key stakeholders, often following an email campaign or event. This approach is particularly crucial for the project when engaging with members of the 6G, microelectronics and policymakers.	6G & Microelectronics Ecosystems, Partnerships & Networks, Policymakers

Table 1. Direct Engagement

Digital Channels			
Measure	Description	Benefit of measure	Stakeholders
Project Website	Establish an online platform - a website where the general public and stakeholders can retrieve details on the project's advancements and outcomes, news, articles, and public deliverables.	The project website plays a vital role in enhancing the project's visibility, acquainting visitors with 6G-REFERENCE's purpose, and introducing them to the project's concept. All project public outcomes are uploaded on the website to allow individuals interested in the topic to monitor the project's advancement while optimising the website to boost 6G-REFERENCE's visibility on search engines.	All Stakeholders
Social Media	6G-REFERENCE will actively engage with communities on social media platforms, particularly Twitter and LinkedIn, which have proven effective in reaching and connecting with individuals within this sector.	Social media platforms offer a cost-effective and efficient way to engage with diverse interest groups and communities who may not typically participate in traditional events or conferences, both in-person and online.	All Stakeholders
Newsletters	An online newsletter will summarise the key activities and achievements in addition to the email communication. The project aims to contribute to other initiatives' newsletters. Utilising professional marketing platforms will automate distribution to all contacts.	The newsletter informs the stakeholders about the project's advancements and sustains their engagement.	6G & Microelectronics Ecosystems, Partnerships & Networks
Press Releases	6G-REFERENCE plans to generate press releases for mainstream and specialised media newsletters, magazines, and journals. Additionally, partners will independently disseminate press releases to inform their customer, member, and collaborator networks about the project.	Press releases can be tailored to specific stakeholder groups based on the publication or website where they are published or distributed. This allows for a more focused and effective message that resonates with the interests and needs of the target audience.	6G & Microelectronics Ecosystems, Partnerships & Networks
Referrals	Establishment of a robust network of involved stakeholders collaborating to attain the project's goals and advocate for sustainable development within their domains.	To enhance project visibility and gain momentum, 6G-REFERENCE will execute a referral strategy leveraging its partners' communication channels and initiatives.	6G & Microelectronics Ecosystems

Table 2. Digital Channels for Communication

Promotion Material			
Measure	Description	Benefit of measure	Stakeholders
Branding & Templates	To ensure brand consistency, the project will maintain a recognisable visual identity, messaging, and tone of voice across all communication channels.	Visual content has proven to be a highly effective communication strategy, enhancing engagement and understanding by conveying complex information clearly and concisely.	All Stakeholders
Slide Decks	Slide decks often serve as the initial introduction to a project, especially during events, email campaigns, and individual meetings. The project will develop various versions of slide decks to effectively engage different audiences, tailoring the content and presentation to resonate with each specific group.		6G & Microelectronics Ecosystems, Partnerships & Networks
Infographics & Banners	Infographics and banners serve as powerful visual tools for grabbing attention and conveying information about the project, its goals, announcements, partners, and beneficiaries. The project incorporates these elements into its website, social media platforms, and newsletters, creating a cohesive visual experience and ensuring consistent messaging across all communication channels.		All Stakeholders
Multimedia Material	The project will leverage multimedia content, including video interviews and animations, to provide a visually engaging and self-explanatory presentation of its activities. These materials will be distributed through various channels, such as YouTube, effectively promoting the project and reaching a wider audience. The video interviews will be conducted during plenary meetings and relevant events, capturing valuable insights and perspectives. The final product will involve editing these interviews alongside animations and creating a compelling and informative presentation of the project.		All Stakeholders

<p>Printing & Merchandising</p>	<p>The project's promotional materials will primarily consist of brochures, catalogues, posters, and other printed resources. To ensure sustainability and accessibility, most of these materials will be available in electronic format, with printed copies provided on demand for events, workshops, and similar gatherings. This approach has proven effective in reaching a wider audience and promoting project initiatives.</p>	<p>The project will leverage promotional materials distributed at events, conferences, workshops, and other occasions to increase its visibility and reach a broader audience, including the general public and national and European media.</p>	<p>All Stakeholders</p>
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Table 3. Promotion Material

3.1.4. 6G-REFERENCE Branding

The project logo (**Figure 8**) serves as a central element of the visual identity. The "6G-REFERENCE Brand Guidelines⁷" provide detailed information on the various logo formats available. Partners can access these formats through the online project folder, ensuring consistent and appropriate use of the logo.

Figure 8. Project Logos

Additionally, the project utilises two specific fonts⁸:

Titles: **Rajdhani Bold**

Normal Text: Rajdhani Medium

Only these fonts are permitted for use in the project's publications and presentations.

The project colours are as follows:

- Primary: #1C487D
- Secondary: #1CCAC9 | #1C89A3 | #FFB430
- Neutrals: #FFFFFF | #000000

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/10804367>

⁸ <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Rajdhani>

Color

Introduction to the selected color palette for a brand

The brand's color scheme includes the primary, secondary, accent (or exception to use in case of an error), and neutral colors such as white or black.

The primary color is the most dominant and recognizable color of the brand, followed by the secondary colors that complement and contrast with the primary color. The secondary colors are ordered according to the priority indicated in the diagram on the right, where the top color has higher priority than the bottom color. Refer to the diagram on the right for specific colors and their contrast ratio*.

Source:
www.w3.org/TR/WCAG20/#visual-audio-contrast

Figure 9. Brand Colours

3.1.5. Tools for Internal Communication

Effective and consistent internal communication is crucial for the success of the 6G-REFERENCE project. The project team, consisting of ten partner organisations, relies on seamless communication to achieve the established research and innovation goals. To facilitate this, the project has implemented various communication tools:

- **Collaborative online workspace:** Partners utilise a secure SharePoint platform to store internal work documents, accessible only to authorised members of the partner organisations.
- **Virtual work meetings:** The leader of each Work Package (WP) organises regular virtual meetings to synchronise work across different WP tasks. These meetings provide a platform for WP leaders to update the project coordinator and the entire consortium on progress and plans.
- **Mailing lists:** This communication tool serves administrative purposes, including facilitating important decision-making and reporting project progress to the European Commission.

3.2. Dissemination Strategy

Dissemination plays a vital role in maximising the impact of research and innovation projects. According to the European Commission, "Dissemination involves sharing research findings with potential users - peers in the research community, industry, other commercial entities, and policymakers. By disseminating research outcomes within the scientific community, you contribute to the advancement of science as a whole." Recognising this importance, the 6G-REFERENCE project has developed a comprehensive and adaptable Dissemination Plan. This plan aims to effectively raise awareness about the project's results, foster understanding, and encourage action among the identified key target audience. The plan's implementation will support the optimal utilisation and adoption of the outcomes and research insights generated throughout the project's duration, ultimately reinforcing each of the intended impacts outlined in the work plan.

3.2.1. Objectives

The dissemination strategy aims to achieve the following key objectives:

- Establishing the dissemination mechanisms and priorities of 6G-REFERENCE.
- Cultivating a community centred around 6G-REFERENCE in alignment with the stakeholder management Plans.
- Increasing visibility and advocating for the work and outcomes to target stakeholders through the creation of promotional materials and information campaigns.
- Sharing the project and its results with a wide audience using diverse channels and tools. Encouraging external participation and knowledge exchange through networking activities and events to enhance the potential impact and contributions to the project.
- Shaping policy decisions, sparking future research, elevating awareness, bolstering the SNS Joint Undertaking, and fostering innovation within the industry.
- Collaborating with other EU, national, international, and SNS initiatives to optimise impact.

3.2.2. Phases

The project's dissemination strategy will be implemented in a phased approach, with three distinct phases (**Figure 10**), each focusing on specific objectives and utilising appropriate channels for targeted action. These phases were initially outlined and discussed at the project's inception and will be continuously refined to ensure alignment with 6G-REFERENCE's evolving priorities.

Figure 10. Dissemination Plan Phases

The dissemination activities for the 6G-REFERENCE project will be implemented in three distinct phases, each with specific objectives and corresponding actions:

Phase I – Analysis (Months 1-9): This initial phase will focus on analysing the project's framework, identifying potential barriers to dissemination, and defining priorities and actions for the first year. The Communication & Dissemination Leader will oversee engagement efforts to align dissemination activities with stakeholder needs, fostering general awareness about the project's objectives and anticipated outcomes. Branding materials and an initial set of promotional materials will be prepared and delivered as outlined in the 6G-REFERENCE communication plan.

Phase II – Increased Impact (Months 9-18): The key goal of Phase II is to amplify the impact and recognition achieved in Phase I, showcasing the accomplishments of 6G-REFERENCE. The Communication & Dissemination Leader will customise the channels and strategies identified during the proposal phase (and refined in Phase I) to meet the specific demands of Phase II. The focus will be on effectively engaging and collaborating with target groups to maximise the impact of the project's results. Participation in workshops, tailored event planning, and the possibility of hosting tutorials/webinars will enrich the dissemination process. Additionally, specific PR materials will be developed.

Phase III – Adoption (Months 18-36): This phase will leverage the awareness generated in Phases I and II to attract more potential users and customers to the 6G-REFERENCE project outcomes. The Communication & Dissemination Leader, in partnership with the Exploitation Leader, will evaluate the results of Phases I and II and adjust priorities, channels, and strategies as needed. This will be carried out in conjunction with agile stakeholder management activities. Furthermore, plans will be made for activities that can have a lasting impact beyond the project's duration, including ongoing event participation, workshops and conference engagement, and contributions to targeted online and print media publications.

3.2.3. Measures

To ensure the successful execution of the dissemination plan, the consortium has outlined a series of key actions to be taken throughout the project's duration, aimed at achieving the stated objectives in a timely and effective manner.

Dissemination Material			
Measure	Description	Benefit of measure	Stakeholders
Project Documentation	Comprehensive documentation facilitating the replication of the project's technical and scientific achievements, including methodologies, APIs, system architectures, models, guidelines, recommendations, promotional strategies, and other valuable insights	Open information can be disseminated to stakeholder ecosystems to foster collaboration, knowledge sharing, and potential future application development.	6G & Microelectronics Ecosystems, Policymakers
Peer-reviewed Publications	Sharing its technical achievements and findings with the 6G and microelectronics innovation community through publications in esteemed scientific journals and	Share the project's findings with the scientific community, facilitating the dissemination of results and	6G & Microelectronics Ecosystems

	conferences, capitalising on the consortium's expertise.	enabling further research and application.	
Awareness Publications	<p>It is crucial to raise awareness of 6G solutions among a wide audience. Through targeted publications, including articles, blog posts, and fact sheets, we will simplify complex project insights for non-technical audiences, highlighting the European Commission's key role and the benefits of 6G technology. This outreach will be achieved through prominent sources like the EU Research & Innovation Magazine, Digital Innovation Magazine, and Industry Europe, in collaboration with the CORDIS editorial team.</p>	<p>Targeted articles can amplify the project's visibility, sharing its insights and outcomes with a broader scientific and technical community and amplifying its influence.</p>	<p>6G & Microelectronics Ecosystems, Partnerships & Networks, App Sectors, Society</p>
Guidelines	<p>The project will establish a set of comprehensive guidelines to support external development, encompassing essential resources such as a code of ethics, development frameworks, security protocols, standards, debugging tools, and performance optimisation considerations.</p>	<p>Improved the overall quality and security of developed solutions, facilitating knowledge sharing and increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of development efforts</p>	<p>6G & Microelectronics Ecosystems, Partnerships & Networks</p>
Insight Paper	<p>The document will share valuable insights and best practices from the project's implementation and validation stages, focusing on informing policymakers and proposing solutions to address challenges.</p>	<p>This measure benefits stakeholders by strengthening the European microelectronics industry's capabilities in providing communication solutions, thereby supporting the EU's digital transformation agenda. The resulting document will offer valuable insights and best practices from the project's implementation and validation stages.</p>	<p>6G & Microelectronics Ecosystems, Partnerships & Networks, Policymakers</p>

Table 4. Dissemination Material

Digital Channels			
Measure	Description	Benefit of measure	Stakeholders
Source Code Repository	Promotion replicability and transparency by ensuring easy access to our software repositories on popular source code management platforms such as GitHub or GitLab.	This strategy will support the implementation of key principles like transparency, openness, and vendor-neutral partnerships.	6G Ecosystems
Open Access to Research	Following the 'as open as possible' principle, 6G-REFERENCE provides unrestricted access to peer-reviewed publications and scientific research data. The project utilises the Zenodo OpenAIRE+ repository for publishing publications and data, with tools for establishing connections between them. Zenodo serves as the document repository for all public deliverables, and materials are openly shared through data.europa.eu whenever possible.	By making scientific and technical materials openly accessible, the project can reach a wider audience in the scientific and technological community.	6G & Microelectronics Ecosystems
Helpdesk	A designated contact point (info@6greference.eu) will address general inquiries, collaboration requests, bug tracking, and feature requests, with a commitment to respond within 48 hours.	This ensures that inquiries and requests are promptly addressed, leading to better collaboration, faster issue resolution, and increased stakeholder satisfaction.	All Stakeholders
Online Forms	The project will gather information and feedback through online forms using EUSurvey, the EC's official tool for surveys, questionnaires, application forms, and registration forms, ensuring full GDPR compliance.	Enhanced data security and compliance with GDPR regulations. This measure ensures that data collected through surveys, questionnaires, application forms, and registration forms is handled securely and privacy-compliant, building trust with respondents and safeguarding their personal information.	All Stakeholders
Portals	The project will utilise EU-funded project services like the Horizon Results Platform and Dealflow.eu, along with sector-specific sites such as the SNS Project Portfolio.	This approach aims to target specific audiences, boost visibility, and build credibility in the relevant community. It also simplifies dissemination and encourages more stakeholder engagement.	6G & Microelectronics Ecosystems, Partnerships & Networks

Table 5. Digital Channels for Dissemination

Outreach Events			
Measure	Description	Benefit of measure	Stakeholders
Webinars / Workshops	Participate in workshops and webinars for 6G technology training and idea exchange, catering to both consortium members and the public. Webinars will be recorded, edited, and shared as educational resources.	Participating in and hosting/co-hosting workshops and webinars is a strategic approach to actively engaging with multiple stakeholders.	6G & Microelectronics Ecosystem, Partnerships & Networks, App Sectors
Conferences / Fairs	Participating in conferences and trade fairs provides a platform to interact with a diverse range of stakeholders simultaneously, covering both European and global perspectives.	Showcasing the project's tangible outcomes through exhibitions and demonstration events allows for the dissemination of concrete results to a wider audience.	All Stakeholders
Working Groups	The strength of 6G-REFERENCE lies in the consortium's active engagement in working groups. These task forces unite community efforts to facilitate shared discussions and strategies, with a focus on fostering technical and promotional collaborations.	Task forces facilitate collaborative efforts, fostering shared discussions and strategies among community members. They focus on creating synergies that leverage both technical expertise and promotional capabilities.	6G & Microelectronics Ecosystems, Partnerships & Networks

Table 6. Outreach Events

3.2.4. Major Event List

Below in **Table 7** are listed the major yearly events that 6G-reference will be present.

Events	Date	Short description
EU Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC)	3-6 June 2024, 2025 and 2026 editions	Conference supported by the European Commission, project booth at the exhibition
6G Summit	3-6 June 2024, 2025 and 2026 editions	Telecommunications conference, project booth at the exhibition
Mobile World Congress	3-6 March 2024, 2025 and 2026 editions	Flagship mobile industry and technology event, project booth at the exhibition

Table 7. Event List

Below in **Table 8** are listed the major Conferences and Journal that 6G-reference will be disseminate and publish its results.

3.2.5. Conference & Journal List

Title	Type
IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits (JSSC)	Journal
IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications	Journal
IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation	Journal
IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems (TCAS)	Journal
IEEE Communication Magazine	Journal
Journal on Selected Areas in Communications (JSAC)	Journal
IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM)	Conference
European Microwave Week (EuMW), Radar (EuRAD) and Microwave Component (EuMC) Conference	Conference
International Solid-State Circuits Conference (ISSCC)	Conference
European Solid-State Electronics Research Conference (ESSERC, previously ESSCIRC)	Conference
IEEE Symposium on Joint Communications and Sensing	Conference
Radio Frequency Integrated Circuits Conference (RFIC)	Conference
SBMO/IEEE MTT-S International Microwave and Optoelectronics Conference	Conference
International Microwave Symposium (IMS)	Conference
European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EUCAP)	Conference

Table 8. Conferences & Journal List

3.3. Monitoring and Risk Mitigation

3.3.1. Monitoring Strategy

Ongoing monitoring and adaptation of the Communication & Dissemination plan is vital to the project's overall success. By continuously tracking progress, the consortium can swiftly identify and rectify any deviations, optimising effectiveness by implementing corrective measures as needed. This process enables the consortium to proactively address potential implementation challenges and determine whether additional actions are required to achieve the objectives. Particular emphasis is placed on pre-assessing information requirements, monitoring frequency (on a monthly basis), and the methodology for gathering evidence. The successful execution of the Communication & Dissemination plan relies on a monitor and response system (**Figure 11**). Each activity will be closely monitored and assessed based on its impact. It is directly linked to the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and the guidelines outlined in the Communication & Dissemination section (see annex for Communication & Dissemination KPIs & Guidelines).

Figure 11. Monitoring Activity Phases

The monitoring process involves a cyclical approach:

Design: Activities are designed to align with the Communication & Dissemination Plan.

Execute: Activities are executed according to plan.

Monitor: Activities are closely tracked, and feedback and results are gathered using a template accessible only to partners via the internal website.

Evaluate: Outcomes are collaboratively evaluated against targets set during the design phase.

Learn: Valuable insights are extracted from the assessment process.

Adjust: Findings and feedback are incorporated to modify the plan as necessary.

All outcomes and results of the Communication & Dissemination Plan will be comprehensively documented in the **D5.2 Dissemination, Communication & Engagement Intermediate Report** at Month 18 and the **D5.3 Dissemination, Communication & Engagement Final Report** at Month 36.

3.3.2. Risks and Mitigation Strategies

The project's communication and dissemination components are susceptible to several risks and potential pitfalls, which the Communication & Dissemination Leader will proactively monitor and address through regular risk evaluations and timely reporting to the Project Coordinator, with a focus on mitigating issues such as:

Communication & Dissemination Risks		
Risk	Level	Measure to Minimise Risk
Low impact of promotional channels	Medium	The project will regularly evaluate its marketing campaigns, assessing their effectiveness and identifying areas for improvement. It will also explore new opportunities for outreach and engagement, including participation in pertinent events throughout the project's duration.
Low engagement with the community	Medium	The 6G-REFERENCE project will employ a flexible and adaptive stakeholder management approach grounded in agile methodologies to ensure that its target audience and engagement strategies remain relevant and effective throughout the project's lifespan. Rather than relying on a static list of profiles, the project will regularly reassess and refine its approach based on feedback and interactions with stakeholders.
Insufficient or limited engagement from partners	High	The 6G-REFERENCE consortium has developed a comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy supported by detailed internal guidelines and manuals, as well as rigorous monitoring and evaluation processes. These resources empower partners to assess the project's progress and engagement levels, both in terms of quantitative metrics and qualitative feedback.

Table 9. Communication/Dissemination Risks and Mitigation Measures

4. Exploitation & Sustainability Plans

4.1. Objectives

6G-REFERENCE recognizes three main exploitation models for the project results:

Commercial exploitation model: The paid provision of the project results to the end users, complying with a licensing scheme that will be defined at a later stage.

Research exploitation model: The use of the research know-how acquired in future research activities.

Technological exploitation model: The use of the technological know-how gained for the development of innovative products and the provision of advanced services built on top of them.

All three routes will be explored independently as the project evolves while the most appropriate exploitation model will be selected. However, it also needs to be addressed that the exploitation models of the project's results will be dependent upon three main parameters:

- The nature and interests of the project partners and stakeholders in general.
- The distribution model (commercial or non-commercial) of the project results.
- The distribution of the IPRs amongst the project partners.
- The expected TRL of each Exploitable Asset.

Based on these limitations:

6G-REFERENCE industrial partners are mainly interested in technological exploiting the project results, the consortium (as well as external) academic and research organizations are mainly interested in adopting the research exploitation model for project results integrating them in their research and/or teaching activities, and setting up future research projects further promoting the project results, and external industrial partners are mainly interested in adopting the technological exploitation model for the project results.

The exploitation plan for the 6G-REFERENCE project is based on the expected outcome during the project duration. The intensity and amount of information that can be made available from the results will vary over time during the project lifetime. In addition, different exploitable assets such as IPRs will be exploited by different stakeholders based on the management of IPRs. The project's exploitation strategy will comprise activities which include:

- In the project identify innovative and exploitable assets, whether these are scientific results or technological components.
- Based on the consortium agreement (CA), have an outlined management of IPRs.
- Exploitation activities through the project's demonstrators.

4.2. 6G-REFERENCE Added Value

Although 6G is still far from well-defined, the consensus is that more spectrum and further network densification will be needed to cope with the ever-increasing traffic demands and the population densification in urban areas. It is widely expected that distributed MIMO (D-MIMO) communication will become a key enabler for densification in 6G, e.g., exploiting cell-free networks and user-centric massive MIMO techniques. Indeed, if users are surrounded by antennas, joint cooperative transmission of a group of wireless Access Points (APs) can potentially allow for frequency re-use on a very dense scale. What is often not sufficiently appreciated is the tough timing synchronisation requirements that come with such architectures.

6G-REFERENCE will address challenging HW requirements for D-MIMO in the new frequency range of 10-15 GHz. Hardware for integrated communication and sensing in D-MIMO systems where new solutions are needed for synchronization and full-duplex are the main changes to be addressed in 6G-REFERENCE.

4.3. Exploitation Strategy and Expected KERs

4.3.1. Plan

6G-REFERENCE aims to establish itself as a sustainable project in the long run by consolidating its assets and ensuring their development. The exploitation plan for each project's exploitable result will be developed and revised based on the evolving needs and progress of the 6G-REFERENCE project over its duration. As the 6G-REFERENCE project progresses, the exploitation plan can be structured into several phases:

1. **Initial Assessment:** Evaluate the potential exploitable results generated by the project.
2. **IPR Management:** Establish clear IPR management protocols to secure and distribute intellectual property rights among project partners effectively (which are specified in the Consortium Agreement)
3. **Exploitation Model Categorisation:** Based on the expected outcomes nature (TRL), interests of the project partners and IPR generated.
4. **Individual and Joint Exploitation:** It will be chosen based on intellectual property rights generated, aligning with the varying interests and technological readiness levels of the project partners.
5. **Implementation:** Commercial, research, and technological model Implementation
6. **Monitoring and Optimization:** Continuously monitor the progress of exploitation activities, refine strategies.
7. **Define Licensing Schemes:** Develop clear licensing schemes based on IPR.
8. **Research Integration:** Integrate research know-how into future research activities of academic and research organizations
9. **Technical Integration:** Integrate technical solutions into systems (products & services) to enhance functionality and performance.

The project plans to develop new scientific and technical knowledge and grant access to foreground Intellectual Property through royalty-based access rights. It also explores

the feasibility of new technology, products, processes, services, and solutions. To ensure sustainable development of the project outcomes, and commercial monetisation in some cases, 6G-REFERENCE brings together a consortium with key industrial presence (including both large and small companies) that covers the market and sectorial needs required in the value chain.

The consortium is committed to the sustainability of the project's results. The overall strategy includes a thorough assessment of each partner's ambition towards research priorities, business development strategies, and contribution to the standardisation landscape. The project plans to explore new market and revenue opportunities and collaborate with customers, new stakeholders, developer communities, start-up incubators, and Venture capital investors. Exploitation will be performed across various axes, depending on the participant type (industry, SME or academia). Overall, 6G-REFERENCE is committed to ensuring the sustainable development of its assets and outcomes by collaborating with a strong consortium and exploring new opportunities in the market.

4.3.2. Expected Key Exploitable Results

6G-REFERENCE has identified potential Key Exploitable Results (KERs) listed below and indicate the measures on how they are meant to be exploited.

KER #1: Programmable IF FIR-Filtering, delay and downconversion
<p>Short Description: The IF FIR filtering technologies to be developed and demonstrated in this project are potentially exploitable in many different Rx systems. Also, the linear phase property of FIR-filters can provide delay, which can be exploited to for instance realize IF-beamforming, cancel delayed SI, and improve bandwidth of RF-SIC.</p> <p>Exploitation Strategy: This 6G-REFERENCE project aims to demonstrate feasibility and explore new architectures. These could be patented by an interested company. Also, scientific publications in IEEE JSSC or IEEE conferences like ISSCC, RFIC and ESCCIRC are expected as result.</p> <p>Background IP: UT has developed an FIR-filter based RF receiver in cooperation with Huawei, which was patented [Hui22]. Note that delay-exploitation was not patented, and alternative circuit implementations are likely also patentable.</p>
KER #2: Antenna elements and array technologies
<p>Short Description: Two different antenna array technologies to be developed and demonstrated in this project are potentially exploitable. The first one includes high isolation Tx-Rx elements and the filtering-antenna integration scheme to enhance the frequency selectivity of the antennas in order to cope with the coexistence with other applications over the 10-15 GHz band. The second one is the integration structure and interconnects between RF front-end chip/modules and waveguide-based antenna arrays. Besides, the concept of integrating in an antenna single element gas detection is exploitable and aims to coexist for communications and air quality monitoring. The spatial-domain SIC is an enabler for FD communication and monostatic sensing.</p> <p>Exploitation Strategy: The two integrated antenna array structures and the single antenna sensing element are potentially patentable. UB, in collaboration with CTTC and ANT, intend to explore opportunities for patenting unique developed designs. We also intend to disseminate the results through scientific publications in top-tier IEEE journals or international conferences such as EUCAP, EUMC or IMS. For IMEC, the spatial-domain SIC has a high potential in 6G radios, including ISAC.</p> <p>Background IP: UB has significant know-how on integrated antennas. We intend to generate new IPs within the scope of this project. CTTC has significant know-how on microwave circuits and electromagnetic sensors. ANT has significant know-how on planar to waveguide interconnect design and implementation. CTTC is currently filing a</p>

patent on sensing using microwave circuits and signals, this will be a key background IP owned by CTTC. 6G-REFERENCE partners CTTC, UB and ANT will work within this project to generate new IP under appropriate IP agreements. The spatial-domain SIC could lead to new IP by IMEC if innovative solutions are generated.

KER #3: RIS

Short Description: We propose to develop new reconfigurable intelligent surfaces enabled by using liquid metal and microfluidics based tuning technologies. Temperature and pressure proof of concept sensors will be developed that can be embedded as part of the reconfigurable intelligent surface.

Exploitation Strategy: In general, RIS is a rapidly developing technology with ample exploitation opportunities. We will primarily look into patent opportunities from new tuning techniques, and integrated sensor configurations. We also intend to disseminate the results through scientific publications in top-tier IEEE journals or international conferences such as EUMC, EUCAP, or IMS.

Background IP: UB has filed a patent on liquid metal based tuning devices. This would be a key background IP owned by UB. 6G-REFERENCE partners UB, CTTC and ANT will work within this project to generate new IP under appropriate IP agreements.

KER #4: Over the Air Synchronization and high-resolution time-stamping

Short Description: The FDSYNC concept theoretically allows for improved frequency and timing synchronization. Moreover, new jitter cleaning techniques and high-resolution time-stamping techniques building on sub-sampling phase detection [Gao10] will be developed.

Exploitation Strategy: This project aims to demonstrate the feasibility of OAS FDSYNC with high-resolution time-stamping. This could be patented by an interested company. Also, scientific publications in IEEE JSSC or IEEE conferences like ISSCC, RFIC and ESCCIRC are expected as result.

Background IP: UT has pioneered the now very popular sub-sampling PLL technique in cooperation with National Semiconductors and patented it [Gao10]. FDSYNC and time-stamping exploiting sub-sampling was not yet patented.

KER #5: Time-Modulated Array (TMA) and Frequency-Modulated Array (FMA)

Short Description: The Time-Modulated Array (TMA) architecture and the Frequency-Modulated Array (FMA) are two dynamic array schemes, whose time-varying patterns break the fundamental limits of the conventional static phased arrays or MIMOs with time-invariant patterns. The TMA achieves concurrent multi-beam MIMO operations with very low hardware overhead and complexity, and TMA performance can be enhanced by signal processing and optimization of the time modulation sequences. The FMA achieves super-resolution in angular resolution of detecting multiple targets or localizing multiple TX/RX nodes. FMA is also fully compatible with various radar schemes, such as FMCW chirped radar for depth and speed detection.

Exploitation Strategy: This project focus on demonstrating the feasibility of extending TMA and FMA to both TX and RX arrays. This project will also explore new signal processing of time modulation sequences for TMAs and frequency modulation schemes for FMAs. ETHZ Technology Transfer Office (ETH Transfer) will patent the ETHZ research results and will actively seek IP licensing with interested industry partners. In parallel, scientific publications in IEEE journals of JSSC and T-MTT or IEEE conferences like ISSCC, RFIC and ESCCIRC will be expected research outcomes as well.

Background IP: The TMA and FMA dynamic array concepts were first developed during PI Wang's transition from Georgia Institute of Technology (USA) and ETHZ (Switzerland). The FMA concept in wireless TRX for super-resolution localization and radar as well as its operations with new frequency-modulation waveforms was patented by Georgia Tech Technology Transfer Office [Man22b]. The TMA concept for concurrent multi-beam MIMO TRX, its use in various wireless systems (hybrid beamforming, radar, repeaters) and use with various time-modulation waveforms was patented by ETHZ Technology Transfer Office. Both Georgia Tech and ETHZ Technology Transfer Offices work extensively with industry for IP licensing.

4.4. Knowledge Management and Protection Strategy

6G-REFERENCE will consider three main elements of an effective system to protect and exploit Intellectual Property (IP). Firstly, a system that enables the **protection of IP** (e.g. patents, copyrights, brand, industrial design) that includes clarity about the ownership and use of IP rights (IPR), the rights and freedom of parties to transfer (assign) IP, and the freedom to publish. Secondly, a **technology transfer framework**, preferably with the support of specialised knowledge transfer offices with professional staff, such as the [European IPR Helpdesk](#). Thirdly, a **fair law enforcement system** in each partner's country caters to dispute settlement and can award penalties and sanctions where appropriate. The basic principle is that foreground knowledge, i.e. created within (or resulting from) the project, belongs to the project partner who generated it. If knowledge is developed jointly and separate parts cannot be distinguished, it will be jointly owned unless the contractor concerned agree on a different solution. Regarding background and granting Access Rights for the execution of work during the project this is regulated by the Consortium Agreement.

Literary works, software, databases, PR material (e.g. website) and training material will be protected by copyright (e.g. ©6G-REFERENCE Project, All rights reserved), and 6G-REFERENCE will select an appropriate type of Creative Common licenses, for Literary works, PR material (e.g. website) and training material, most likely the 4.0 international license suite, to determine the terms of distribution. Any third-party user will be asked to agree with the license by clicking the CC button to convey the basic permissions associated with material offered under CC licenses and communicate to users the permissions granted in advance.

4.5. Exploitation & Sustainability Tools

Scientific results will be exploited mainly by publishing in highly ranked journal of conferences as well as through dissemination workshops. Technological components will be showcased by the demos outlined in the project. Project result will also be exploited to impact regulatory- and standardization organisations. On the project website, a simple list will be provided to track and report all efforts linked to communication, dissemination and exploitation of the project and its results. This is a collective effort to which all partners should contribute. Whenever a partner participates in a communication or dissemination action/activity or dedicates efforts/resources to contribute and drive the project exploitation strategy, it needs to be reported to keep full traceability and collect evidence for the European Commission. The success of dense cell-free deployments will depend on its sustainability and scalability, that in turn will be highly impacted by the design of each distributed radio. Therefore, 6G-REFERENCE will explore low complexity, low cost, and low power consumption hardware solutions still providing enhanced capabilities to meet the new 6G needs in a sustainable way.

5. Standardisation Plans

Ensuring standardisation is crucial for effectively leveraging developed project outcomes. Consequently, 6G-REFERENCE is dedicated to establishing a close two-way connection with 3GPP working groups. New data and solutions are assessed for ongoing and future standardisation efforts. From a microelectronics standpoint, it is vital to define relevant and rational hardware requirements to ensure energy and cost-efficient networks and user devices. The current project serves as a valuable research platform for exploring and pushing the boundaries of microelectronic subsystems, which will impact synchronisation levels to varying extents. These insights can inform the standardisation efforts concerning distributed MIMO and coherent-joint transmission layer mechanisms, necessitating design considerations based on accurate assumptions regarding these uncertainties.

5.1. Objectives

The 6G-REFERENCE will:

- Identify relevant existing standards crucial for the project's operation, taking into account ongoing developments at European and international levels and the relevant technical committees.
- Design a strategy to collaborate with these bodies, including determining the most pertinent ones and the extent of the relationship to be established (e.g., sharing technical information, engaging in ongoing developments, establishing formal partnerships, proposing initiatives, organising joint events, etc.).
- Facilitate and advocate for the integration of project outcomes into future new or updated standards by providing proposals to selected standard development organisations (SDOs) and committees for consideration and inclusion in future standard developments.

5.2. Standardisation Principles

Standardization is key for the successful exploitation of developed project outcomes. Therefore, 6G-REFERENCE is committed to establish a close bidirectional link with relevant 3GPP working groups. In this sense, the role of EAB, as 6G-REFERENCE innovation manager and as a large infrastructure manufacturer, will become fundamental. EAB has strong cross-disciplinary teams continuously supporting standardization work in 3GPP on many different levels. This secures that new data and solutions are considered for current and forthcoming standardization work. And here, from a microelectronics perspective, it is crucial to establish relevant and reasonable requirements on hardware to secure energy and cost-efficient networks and user equipment. 6G-REFERENCE forms an excellent research platform to understand and push the boundaries of microelectronic subsystems that to varying degrees will impact the attainable level of synchronization. Hence, such findings can be used to guide the standardization work of distributed MIMO and coherent-joint transmission layer 1 mechanisms. Such mechanisms need to be designed with regards to correct assumptions on these uncertainties.

5.3. 6G Industry Standards Landscape

3GPP RANx and the **O-RAN Alliance** (possibly **ETSI-MSG**) are the main standardization bodies that are relevant for 6G-REFERENCE. From a consortium point of

view both of those are well covered as partners have delegates in those standardization bodies.

5.4. Roadmap for Standardisation Activities

Achieving direct standards modifications is a very challenging task for a hardware-oriented research project. The key is to have a continuous dialog with standardization delegates belonging to partners in the consortium to learn from them as well as teach what is possible from a technical point of view. The 6G-REFERENCE consortium has been already designed to meet these interdisciplinary needs. EAB, will be the main industrial anchor with strong connection to standardization activities, which will ensure alignment with the future commercial needs.

The way 6G-REFERENCE will facilitate standardization work is to have contact with delegates on topics related to DMIMO coherent-joint transmission and sensing by providing specific information of the capabilities and limitations of underlying hardware.

Timeline:

For the frequency bands in the 10-15 GHz range that 6G-REFERENCE will work on, the standardization in 3GPP has not started yet. A few technical reports have been concluded, but the real standardization effort for this frequency range is expected to start the second half of 2025. Technical solutions and “realistic” hardware requirements developed in 6G-REFERENCE will be discussed with standardization delegates from projects partners to influence the standardization work but also for the project to receive valuable information regarding requirements. From the project it is believed that this is the most efficient method.

The timing for the 6G-REFERENCE project is good since the project can develop ideas and hardware solutions for about 18 months before the expected standardization work in 3GPP starts. The second half of the project time, standardization activities can be followed and results from 6G-REFERENCE, where suitable, can be used as input to the standardization discussions.

6. Conclusions

In Horizon Europe, projects and strategies for communication, dissemination, standardisation, and exploitation aim to extend project impacts beyond research outcomes alone. 6G-REFERENCE has developed a comprehensive communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan to uphold these strategies throughout the project's duration.

This document will serve as a foundation for ongoing and future communication activities, with continuous monitoring and updates planned. For communication and dissemination, 6G-REFERENCE plans to share project results at key stages to demonstrate how research and innovation contribute to the European 'Innovation Union'. Communication efforts will emphasise the diverse European consortium's scientific excellence and competitive contributions through targeted outreach to various stakeholders. Multiple channels will be utilised for broad visibility and project promotion, including social networks, events, media, publications, conferences, and email marketing. Simultaneously, PR campaigns will keep stakeholders informed about 6G-REFERENCE's progress and outcomes, aligning communications with the project's goals. A metrics system will assess the effectiveness of these efforts and ensure alignment with predefined objectives.

Regarding exploitation, 6G-REFERENCE's consortium will continually evaluate project outcomes, explore potential avenues for exploitation, and identify the most promising pathways for each asset. Various exploitation routes, such as individual or collaborative, scientific, commercial, and technical, will be considered for sustainable impact post-project. Proactive management of intellectual property rights will ensure proper valuation and preservation of research findings, potentially generating revenue for partners after project completion.

7. Appendix

7.1. Key Performance Indicators

Type of KPI	Material	Target KPI	Description
Communication	Press Release	1+	Joint & Partner press releases
	Website Traffic	100 unique visitors/month	Measure every four months
	Social media	2000+ followers	Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube followers
	Non-Scientific Articles	50	Publications in articles, blog posts, position papers, factsheets and other non-scientific publications
	Open Access Downloads	1000+	Downloads of public deliverables and documentation through ZENODO
	Webinars & Workshops	6+ 300+ participants	These events facilitate hands-on training and exchange of ideas related to the modules, providing opportunities for round table discussions, mentoring and development.
	Insight Paper	1	Valuable insights and best practices were garnered during the project's implementation and validation stages, with a particular focus on informing policymakers.
	Newsletters	12	6 internal and 6 externals
	Videos	3	Showcasing on results, partners or interviews
Dissemination	Peer-Reviewed Publications	15	5 Journals 10 Conferences
		500+ citations	
	Conferences & Events	15+	Showcases results achieved by the project through presentations, talks, exhibition spaces and personal engagement.
Ecosystem Building	Networks of Contact points	1500+	Overall contacts with whom the project will contact to
	Synergies	4+	Create synergies on joint events, workshops, joint publications, etc.

Table 10. Communication & Dissemination KPIs

7.2. Communication & Dissemination Tools

6G-REFERENCE Website (6greference.eu) has been operational since March 2024 and consists of six distinct pages focused on the project presentation, objectives, challenges, methodology, lexicon, activities, publications, and community.

Figure 12. 6G-REFERENCE Website Home Page

The 6G-REFERENCE LinkedIn page ([6G-REFERENCE](#)) has been operational since February 2024 and has already garnered 365 followers in the first 5 months. A minimum of three new posts are shared on this channel every week.

Figure 13. 6G-REFERENCE LinkedIn Page

SOCIAL MEDIA CALENDAR 2024				
Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday
<p>6G-REFERENCE CTA campaigns:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ---> Visit the website ---> Subscribe to our newsletter ---> Follow us on social media 	<p>6G-REFERENCE Brand:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 6G-REFERENCE website content campaigns: ---> News, articles ---> Interviews ---> PRs ---> Newsletters ---> Scientific Publications ---> Public deliverables 	<p>6G-REFERENCE Brand:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 6G-REFERENCE awareness campaigns: ---> Meet the partners (when possible) ---> Aim/Objectives ---> Challenges ---> Methodology ---> Lexicon ---> Impact ---> Demo cases (when possible) 	<p>Events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ---> Events where we participate ---> Own events ---> Third party events of the ecosystem 	<p>6G-REFERENCE Ecosystem:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ---> SNS-JU activities: news, events, publications, milestones, etc. ---> Sibling projects ---> Other 6G and telecommunications associations & organizations ---> General news about the 6G and telecommunications industry, research, innovation ---> EU institutions

Figure 14. Social Media Calendar

The project has been active on the second social media channel, X (@6G_Reference), posting content since February 2024, although it was created before the project launch in December 2023. Currently (June 2024), the project has 110 followers on X. We regularly post new content on this channel a minimum of three times a week.

Figure 15. 6G-REFERENCE X/Twitter Page

The one-pager and roll-up resume for the 6G-REFERENCE project outline its main objectives and actions. These documents are valuable for engaging with stakeholders during meetings, events, and other one-on-one interactions.

Figure 16. 6G-REFERENCE One-Pager

6G + REFERENCE

**6G Hardware Enablers for Cell Free
Coherent Communications and Sensing**

 @6G_Reference
 @6G-REFERENCE
 @6G-REFERENCE

6G-REFERENCE envisions a future where urban areas are equipped with **sustainable solutions** that can cope with the ever-increasing **traffic demands and population densification**, while providing disruptive capabilities like the materialization of the internet of sense.

The 6G-REFERENCE project targets practical integrated circuits (IC) and antenna systems for 6G applications. 6G-REFERENCE will:

Explore radio system operation in the 10-158GHz range

Develop hardware concepts and show feasibility in CMOS

Use additive manufacturing for antenna arrays and nanotechnology for sensors

6GSNS

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101019356. Views and opinions expressed are only those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe's research and innovation programme. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 17. 6G-REFERENCE Roll-up (Banner)

These guidelines will support partners in their contributions to the Dissemination and communication efforts, which are essential for the success of 6G-REFERENCE, by promoting the project’s objectives, activities, and achievements.

Figure 18. 6G-REFERENCE Communication & Dissemination Guidelines

Table of content

Brand Strategy	Vision
	Mission
	Target Audience
	Personality
Visual Tools	Logo
	Colors
	Typography
	Mockups

Figure 19. 6G-REFERENCE Brand Guidelines

6G-REFERENCE utilises the Zenodo OpenAIRE+ repository for depositing publications and data, with tools available to establish connections between them. The Zenodo infrastructure serves as a document repository for all public deliverables. Whenever feasible, datasets are openly shared through data.europa.eu, the EU's official data portal.

Figure 20. 6G-REFERENCE Zenodo Repository

EU logo and acknowledgement

As recipients of EU funding, we have to use the **European flag** and emblem in our communication to acknowledge the support received under EU programs.

Adaptions of this acknowledgement text depending on what is needed for deliveries or submissions.

6G-REFERENCE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No.101139155.

EU disclaimer

It is also necessary the inclusion of the disclaimer in any document delivered within the scope of the project — a statement that denies liability and is intended to prevent civil liability arising from certain acts or omissions.

The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Union, and the European Union is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

Text can appear on the right, left, bottom or top, depending on the needs, and in various fonts.

For more information, please follow the **guidelines** on the use of the EU emblem in the context of EU funding and apply the indicated **graphic rules**.